

Iron(II)-catalysed Debromination of *vic*-Dibromides in *N,N*-Dimethylformamide

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DEBROMINATION of *vic*-dibromides stereospecifically and stereoselectively, to give olefins, has been studied widely¹. Attempts have been made to optimise a number of different reaction conditions involving a variety of reducing agents including metal ions², the most common being zinc, magnesium and halide ions. *meso*-Stilbene dibromide has invariably been chosen as a model substrate.

We undertook the study of debromination to evolve a simple procedure using iron(II) ions and report here a novel method of debromination using a very simple workup. The debromination could be achieved quantitatively by heating the substrate with iron(II) oxalate in dry dimethylformamide at 100° for ~2 h. The progress of the reaction was monitored by tlc. Addition of reaction mixture to dilute H₂SO₄ gave the products which were filtered, dried and characterised (Table 1).

TABLE 1—DEBROMINATION OF *vic*-DIBROMIDES WITH IRON(II) OXALATE IN 1 : 1 MOLAR RATIO IN DMF AT 100°

Halide	Time min	Isolated yield* %
<i>meso</i> -Benzalacetophenone dibromide	75	95
<i>meso</i> -Stilbene dibromide	75	96 ^a
<i>meso</i> -Cinnamic acid dibromide	75	98
<i>meso</i> - <i>p</i> -Nitrobenzalacetophenone dibromide	100	91
<i>meso</i> -Methyl cinnamate dibromide	120	98 ^b
<i>meso</i> -Benzalacetone dibromide	120	92 ^b
<i>trans</i> -1,2-Dibromocyclohexane	180	22 ^c

*Glc analyses showed only *E*-stilbene and no *Z*-stilbene, ^bproduct isolated by extraction with solvent ether as being a low melting solid, ^cHplc analyses showed the presence of cyclohexene (22%) and starting material (78%) after 180 min of refluxing at 150°.

The reaction was very slow at 80° and no debromination was observed in tetrahydrofuran, 1,4-dioxane and acetonitrile as solvents. The debromination could also be achieved by other iron(II) salts. The reaction is best suited for aromatic substrates as debromination of *trans*-1,2-dibromocyclohexane was only 22% complete even after refluxing at 150° for 3 h as monitored by hplc.

Experimental

The products were identified by their m.p., m.m.p. and comparison of ir and nmr spectra with

those of the authentic samples. All the m.ps. were recorded on Tropical Labequip apparatus.

The *vic*-dibromides were prepared by the reported methods. Iron(II) oxalate (Veb Laborchemie Apolda, Germany) was used. Dimethylformamide (B.D.H. and Merck) was used in all reactions after drying.

General procedure : A mixture of the *vic*-dibromide (0.01 mol), iron oxalate (0.01 mol) and dry dimethylformamide was flushed with N₂ gas for 15 min and heated in an oil-bath at 100°. The progress of the reaction was monitored by tlc. After complete debromination, the contents of the flask were poured in 1N H₂SO₄ (200 ml). The mixture was stirred for 5 min and resulting solid was filtered, dried in air, and recrystallised.

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Synthesis of some New Halogenohydroxymethyl Flavones

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CONSIDERING the therapeutic and synthetic importance of chromones¹, it was thought worthwhile to synthesise some new flavones and evaluate their antifungal activity.

The synthesis of the chromones (2) was carried out from the chalcones (1) by oxidative cyclisation using selenium dioxide in isoamyl alcohol. The starting materials 1-(2'-hydroxy-3'/5'-chloro-5'/3'-hydroxymethylphenyl)-3-aryl-2-propen-1-ones (1) were prepared by condensing 2-hydroxy-3/5-chloro-5/3-hydroxymethylacetophenones² with various substituted aromatic aldehydes in presence of alcoholic KOH. In all the flavones, the lowering